

Preliminary Experimental Results for RF Tomography Using Distributed Sensing

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Abstract—Traditional high-value monostatic imaging systems employ frequency-diverse pulses to form images from small synthetic apertures. In contrast, RF tomography utilizes a network of spatially diverse sensors to trade geometric diversity for bandwidth, permitting images to be formed with narrowband waveforms. Such a system could use inexpensive sensors with minimal ADC requirements, provide multiple viewpoints into urban canyons and other obscured environments, and offer graceful performance degradation under sensor attrition. However, numerous challenges must be overcome to field and operate such a system, including multistatic autofocus, precision timing requirements, and the development of appropriate image formation algorithms for large, sparsely populated synthetic apertures with anisotropic targets. AFRL has recently constructed an outdoor testing facility to explore these challenges with measured data. Preliminary experimental results are provided for this system, along with a description of remaining challenges and future research directions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Imaging radars seek to recover a scene reflectivity function by processing backscattered electromagnetic signals. In pulsed imaging systems, the bandwidth of the signal provides range resolution, while narrow-aperture collections of pulses are coherently processed to obtain cross-range resolution, earning the name synthetic aperture radar (SAR) [1].

The radar community realized early on that this processing was analogous to tomographic imaging in the medical community and could be analyzed effectively through the lens of the projection-slice theorem [2]. The analogy is not exact, because the relatively high center frequencies associated with radar signals make radar imaging inherently narrowband and allow the use of small angular apertures to obtain reasonable resolution [3]. Small apertures are used both due to practical limitations on the collection geometry and the reality that point-like scattering features invoked in typical SAR imaging algorithms typically do not persist over the entire viewing sphere [1]. Recently, circular-SAR (CSAR) collections over complete 360° apertures have been investigated [4], [5], but image formation is still typically accomplished by processing small angular sub-apertures [5].

RF tomography seeks to replace relatively wide-band monostatic operation with numerous inexpensive narrowband sensors. Diverse look angles coupled with the collection of bistatic returns allows such a constellation of sensors to

form high-resolution images without using wide bandwidths. Indeed, experimental images have even been formed using monochromatic waveforms [6]. The use of these techniques for localizing moving targets was described in [7] and contrasted with similar techniques in [8]. Reconstructions for RF tomography leveraging sparse regularization techniques were reported in [9] and [10], and a sparse aperture version of the Kaczmarz method was developed in [11]. These techniques have also been applied for use in ground penetrating radar (GPR) applications, e.g., [12].

While the theory of tomographic imaging is well understood [13], a variety of practical challenges must be overcome before these techniques can be used in practical systems. Two principle challenges include determining positions for the possible mobile sensor nodes [14] and coping with specular and anisotropic scattering of targets with complex scattering behavior over wide angular apertures [15], [16], [17]. In order to address these and other challenges, AFRL has constructed an outdoor tomography testbed for generating realistic experimental data to fuel algorithm development. This paper describes the system architecture and capabilities, results from preliminary system validation tests, and plans for future experiments and system refinements.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II summarizes the mathematics underlying RF tomographic imaging. System description and experimental results are presented in Section III, along with discussion and future plans in Section IV. Finally, brief concluding remarks are given in Section V.

II. RF TOMOGRAPHY BACKGROUND

Data from a set of M arbitrary-geometry bistatic scattering experiments will be jointly processed to image the scene. Each scattering experiment will utilize a receiver located at position $\mathbf{r}_m \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and a transmitter at $\mathbf{t}_m \in \mathbb{R}^3$ operating at wavenumber $k_m = \omega_m/c = 2\pi f_m/c$, where c is the speed of propagation. The RF transmission frequency is given in Hertz as f_m . Data in this format can of course be synthesized from a pulsed system by match-filtering and transforming the processed signal to the frequency domain.

Consider an isotropic point scatterer located at an arbitrary point \mathbf{x} . Assuming scalar wave propagation governed by the

Helmholtz equation, the Green's function [13] describing the spherical wave emanating from a point \mathbf{t}_m and impinging on the point \mathbf{x} is given by

$$G(\mathbf{t}_m, \mathbf{x}, k_m) = \frac{e^{jk_m \|\mathbf{t}_m - \mathbf{x}\|_2}}{4\pi \|\mathbf{t}_m - \mathbf{x}\|_2}. \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the wave scattered from \mathbf{x} and measured at \mathbf{r}_m is given as $G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{r}_m, k_m)$. If the scattering potential at \mathbf{x} is given by p , then the measured field for scattering experiment m from the single point target would be

$$e_m = p a_m G(\mathbf{t}_m, \mathbf{x}, k_m) G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{r}_m, k_m), \quad (2)$$

where a_m is the amplitude/phase of the m th transmitted signal. The antenna patterns for the transmit and receive antennas are omitted for simplicity. If we linearize the data model using the Born approximation [13], and discretize the scene into N voxels with locations \mathbf{x}_n and reflectivities p_n , then we can obtain the total measured field for experiment m as

$$e_m = \sum_{n=1}^N p_n a_m G(\mathbf{t}_m, \mathbf{x}_n, k_m) G(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{r}_m, k_m). \quad (3)$$

We can express the complete data collection with a single matrix equation by defining a matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ with $\mathbf{A}_{mn} = a_m G(\mathbf{t}_m, \mathbf{x}_n, k_m) G(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{r}_m, k_m)$. Collect the scattering potentials into a vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ and the measurements into a vector $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{C}^M$. We thus obtain the complete system of equations as

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{n}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ represents additive perturbations to the measurements \mathbf{e} .

Determining the scene reflectivity \mathbf{p} from the measurements \mathbf{e} represents an ill-posed inverse problem that can be solved using a variety of techniques. The problem can be regularized using ℓ_2 or Tikhonov regularization, sparse regularization [10], or other methods. For simplicity and numerical convenience, the initial experimental images in this paper were formed using a time domain implementation of the unfiltered adjoint, i.e., backprojection [18]. Specifically, the reflectivity estimate is calculated as

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{e} \quad (5)$$

$$= \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A} \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{n}. \quad (6)$$

The matrix $\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A}$ characterizes the point spread function (PSF) of the system. For distant isotropic radiators, this matrix will represent a two-dimensional convolution with a spatially-invariant PSF. For close-in sensing, the PSF will vary with the voxel location \mathbf{x}_k . A filter can be applied to the data to shape the PSF, i.e., filtered backprojection. Details can be found in, e.g., [8].

Fig. 1. The “L” shaped target configuration used for the initial experiment is depicted in the inset. The target separation is 3m. The image provides an ariel view of the target location within the sensor ring.

Fig. 2. Image formed from first experiment. While the complete set of frequency data was used for preprocessing, only 50 tones were used to form the final image. The image is in “top-hat space” and is shown on a normalized dB scale.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The AFRL Tomography Range is composed of 12 towers arranged in a circle with a radius of 100m. Each of the towers has two dual-polarized log-periodic antennas elevated 7.62m and 22.86m above the tower base and directed at scene center. Although system upgrades will include the ability to simultaneously transmit arbitrary waveforms, the data described in this paper was acquired with a vector network analyzer (VNA). Coaxial cables connect the dual-polarized transmit and receive channels between the antennas and the VNA. Due to the length of the cables, pre-amplification of the received signal is required.

All of the tests described in this paper utilized the lower ring of antennas with VV polarization measurements only. The targets were wire-mesh top hats measuring 1.22m tall, 1.83m base diameter, and 0.30m top diameter. These targets were selected to capitalize on their nearly uniform scattering

Fig. 3. The four panes show sub-images centered around each of the four target groups. The sub-image around the two target group is 12m by 12m, while the others are 6m by 6m. The three targets separated from the origin are visible but noticeably lower in amplitude.

response as a function of illumination direction and bistatic angle at a given elevation [19]. The initial test used a set of 3 targets in an “L” shape with 3m between each target pair as depicted in Figure 1. The figure provides the target configuration superimposed on an aerial photograph of the ring. A complete set of 20,001 scattering experiments was conducted with the VNA for each of the $\binom{12}{2} = 66$ available bistatic geometries.

Before computing the resulting images, a number of details must be addressed. First, a variety of strong non-cooperative transmitters are illuminating the scene. These signals are filtered from the data before subsequent processing.

Next, the matrix \mathbf{A} in (4) is not completely known in practice. While accurate positions for the sensor locations were measured, the initial gain/phase terms a_m are not known. These unknowns correspond to calibration errors in the cables connecting the antennas to the data collection trailer and various other components in the receiver chain. In addition, our model assumes isotropic scattering from point-like targets. Since the true targets are top hats, the resulting collected data includes an additional multiplication of the data by gain/phase terms accounting for the top-hat response. We can combine these effects into a single unknown multiplication of the data $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^M$. Using \odot to denote the hadamard product, we obtain the new data model as

$$\mathbf{e} = \alpha \odot (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{n}) \quad (7)$$

In addition, the perturbation \mathbf{n} includes strong terms due to background clutter and the direct path signal between the transmitter and each receiver. To address these challenges, three sets of measurements are collected. The first set \mathbf{e}_0 is collected with an empty scene to capture the background scattering and direct path effects. The next data set \mathbf{e}_c places a single top-hat target at the origin. This data provides a measurement of the PSF of the system to a top-hat target

at the origin. Finally, the a data set \mathbf{e}_t is collected using the constellation of targets to be imaged as depicted in Figure 1.

A background subtraction is then performed on both target data sets to partially cancel both the background clutter and direct path signals. We obtain the background subtracted data as $\bar{\mathbf{e}}_c = \mathbf{e}_c - \mathbf{e}_0$ and $\bar{\mathbf{e}}_t = \mathbf{e}_t - \mathbf{e}_0$.

Next, the available wide-bandwidth data is used to range gate the data from each bistatic pair to isolate the target at the origin in $\bar{\mathbf{e}}_c$. This data is then used to estimate the calibration data as $\hat{\alpha} = f(\bar{\mathbf{e}}_c/s_0)$, where the division is elementwise. The vector s_0 represents the expected frequency response of a point target at the origin given a perfectly calibrated system. The function f applies an elementwise lower bound to the amplitude of the calibration estimate.

Finally, we range gate each bistatic pair in $\bar{\mathbf{e}}_t$ to remove energy outside the scene of interest and divide by the estimated calibration data. Bistatic pairs for which the direct path is very close to the scene of interest in range are discarded. The concatenation of these operations corresponds to calibration of the system and an approximate frequency-domain deconvolution with the response of a top-hat target. We then apply a downsampling operator $d(\cdot)$ to eliminate unneeded frequency-domain data and apply backprojection to obtain the final estimated image as

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{A}^H d\left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{e}}_t}{\hat{\alpha}}\right), \quad (8)$$

where the division is again understood to be elementwise.

The resulting image is shown in Figure 2. Since the data was deconvolved with the response of a top hat, the resulting image is in “top-hat space”, which is to say that the image is a plot of an indicator function showing the presence of a top hat centered at each voxel location, i.e., the output of the matched-filter response corresponding to a top-hat signal model. It should be emphasized that wide-band densely spaced frequency data was used to facilitate the preprocessing of the data for removal of background and direct path signals. Although 15,000 tones were used for preprocessing, only 50 tones –spaced evenly over the band from 400 to 1000MHz– were used to form the final image. The envisioned system would accomplish these pre-processing steps without requiring wideband data. A better initial calibration for the system would facilitate this task.

A second experiment was conducted with five targets. Two targets were placed near the origin of the scene 6m apart, while the remaining targets were each placed 20m from the origin in three of the cardinal directions. The processing was the same, except that 200 tones were retained for imaging and the full set of 20,001 tones were used for preprocessing. The resulting images are displayed in Figure 3. The full 1.44 megapixel image is too large to clearly represent here. Instead, a sub-image is displayed showing a region around each target group. While all five targets are visible, the three widely spaced targets have significantly reduced amplitudes. A variety of factors may account for this difference including differences in the antenna patterns, calibration errors magnified by sepa-

ration from the calibration target's location, differences in the elevation response of the top-hat targets, terrain variation, or other effects.

IV. DISCUSSION

A series of pre-processing steps was required using wide-band data before sparse-frequency images could be formed. Background subtraction for removal of clutter is closely related to change detection and does not represent an unreasonable concept of operations. However, the elimination of the direct path signal must be addressed to eliminate the need for range gating. Several approaches are currently being investigated, including the use of multiple simultaneous transmitters [20].

This experiment highlights the necessity for processing techniques to properly account for anisotropic and specular scattering. For example, without the appropriate top-hat model-based deconvolution, standard point-scatterer-based backprojection imaging techniques would have resulted in indecipherably smeared images due to the bistatic response of the targets. Data collected from this range would serve as an ideal testbed for extending multistatic imaging techniques such as the Linear Sampling Method [21], MUSIC [22], level-set-based reconstruction [23], etc, to realistic RF tomography scenarios. Furthermore, RF tomography applications could potentially benefit from dictionary-based reconstructions techniques designs to incorporate anisotropic scattering models [15], [16], [17].

V. CONCLUSION

RF tomography offers the possibility of utilizing a constellation of expendable sensors to form images using minimal spectral bandwidth. Such a system offers multiple viewpoints into urban canyons, offers graceful performance degradation under attrition, and can operate in spectrally cluttered environments. To realize these benefits, a variety of operational challenges must be overcome, including image formation with specular and anisotropic scattering, sensor localization, and direct path cancellation. The results presented here demonstrate the viability of this approach in a less restrictive environment than earlier anechoic chamber work and highlight the remaining technical challenges to real-world application of these techniques.

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REFERENCES

[1] C. V. Jakowatz *et al.*, *Spotlight-Mode Synthetic Aperture Radar: A Signal Processing Approach*. Springer, 1996.
 [2] D. C. Munson, Jr., J. D. O'Brien, and W. K. Jenkins, "A tomographic formulation of spotlight-mode synthetic aperture radar," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 917–925, Aug. 1983.

[3] F. Natterer, M. Cheney, and B. Borden, "Resolution for radar and x-ray tomography," *Inverse Problems*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 55–64, December 2003. [Online]. Available: <http://stacks.iop.org/0266-5611/19/i=6/a=054>
 [4] R. L. Moses and L. C. Potter, "Noncoherent 2d and 3d sar reconstruction from wide-angle measurements," in *13th Annual Adaptive Sensor Array Processing Workshop, MIT Lincoln Laboratory*, 2005.
 [5] E. Ertin, C. D. Austin, S. Sharma, R. L. Moses, and L. C. Potter, "GOTCHA experience report: Three-dimensional SAR imaging with complete circular apertures," in *Algorithms for Synthetic Aperture Radar Imagery XIV*, vol. 6568. SPIE, Apr. 2007.
 [6] M. C. Wicks, B. Himed, J. L. E. Bracken, H. Bascom, and J. Clancy, "Ultra narrow band adaptive tomographic radar," in *Proc. 1st IEEE International Workshop on Computational Advances in Multi-Sensor Adaptive Processing*, 13–15 Dec. 2005, pp. 36–39.
 [7] B. Himed, H. Bascom, J. Clancy, and M. C. Wicks, "Tomography of moving targets (TMT)," in *Sensors, Systems, and Next-Generation Satellites V*, H. Fujisada, J. B. Lurie, and K. Weber, Eds., vol. 4540, no. 1. SPIE, 2001, pp. 608–619.
 [8] M. Cheney and B. Borden, "Imaging moving targets from scattered waves," *Inverse Problems*, vol. 24, no. 3, p. 035005 (22pp), 2008. [Online]. Available: <http://stacks.iop.org/0266-5611/24/035005>
 [9] I. Stojanovic and W. C. Karl, "Imaging of moving targets with multistatic SAR using an overcomplete dictionary," *Submitted to IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, 2009.
 [10] L. C. Potter, E. Ertin, J. T. Parker, and M. Cetin, "Sparsity and compressed sensing in radar imaging," *To Appear in the Proceedings of the IEEE*, 2010.
 [11] R. W. Deming and J. T. Parker, "An iterative inverse-scattering approach to distributed sensing," in *Proc. IEEE Radar Conference*, May 4–8, 2009, pp. 1–5.
 [12] L. Lo Monte, D. Erricolo, F. Soldovieri, and M. C. Wicks, "Radio frequency tomography for tunnel detection," *Geoscience and Remote Sensing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 1128–1137, Mar 2010.
 [13] A. Kak and M. Slaney, *Principles of computerized tomographic imaging*. Institute of Electrical & Electronics Engineers (IEEE), 1988.
 [14] J. T. Parker and J. Norgard, "Autofocusing for RF tomography using particle swarm optimization," in *IEEE Radar Conference*, May 26–30, 2008, pp. 1–6.
 [15] E. Ertin, L. C. Potter, and R. L. Moses, "Enhanced imaging over complete circular apertures," in *Proc. Fortieth Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers ACSSC '06*, Oct.–Nov. 2006, pp. 1580–1584.
 [16] I. Stojanovic, M. Cetin, and W. C. Karl, "Joint space aspect reconstruction of wide-angle SAR exploiting sparsity," in *Proceedings of SPIE*, E. G. Zelnio and F. D. Garber, Eds., vol. 6970, no. 1. SPIE, 2008, p. 697005. [Online]. Available: <http://link.aip.org/link/?PSI/6970/697005/1>
 [17] K. R. Varshney, M. Cetin, J. W. Fisher, and A. S. Willisky, "Sparse representation in structured dictionaries with application to synthetic aperture radar," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 56, no. 8, pp. 3548–3561, Aug. 2008.
 [18] C. J. Nolan and M. Cheney, "Synthetic aperture inversion for arbitrary flight paths and nonflat topography," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 1035–1043, Sept. 2003.
 [19] J. A. Jackson, B. D. Rigling, and R. L. Moses, "Canonical scattering feature models for 3D and bistatic SAR," *To appear in IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 2010.
 [20] L. Lo Monte, L. K. Paton, and M. C. Wicks, "Mitigation of coupling in rf tomography with applications to belowground sensing," in *Proceedings IEEE International Radar Conference*, May 2010.
 [21] D. Colton and A. Kirsch, "A simple method for solving inverse scattering problems in the resonance region," *Inverse Problems*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 383, 1996. [Online]. Available: <http://stacks.iop.org/0266-5611/12/i=4/a=003>
 [22] A. J. Devaney, E. A. Marengo, and F. K. Gruber, "Time-reversal-based imaging and inverse scattering of multiply scattering point targets," *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 118, no. 5, pp. 3129–3138, 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://link.aip.org/link/?JAS/118/3129/1>
 [23] O. Dorn and D. Lesselier, "Level set methods for inverse scattering," *Inverse Problems*, vol. 22, no. 4, p. R67, 2006. [Online]. Available: <http://stacks.iop.org/0266-5611/22/i=4/a=R01>